

TECHNOLOGIES FOR IMPROVING THE PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF INCREASING THE SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF WOMEN

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Abstract. *In this article, we aim to increase the sociopolitical and social activity of women in our country, to create conditions for them to realize their abilities and opportunities in various fields and sectors, and to ensure that their rights and legal interests are unconditionally respected. Additionally, comprehensive support of for motherhood and childhood, as well as the strengthening of family institutions were analysed. These findings indicate the existence of the number of systemic problems and deficiencies that prevent the creation of effective mechanisms for strengthening and improving the moral and moral environment in families. To ensure the existence of a targeted support system for women in need of help and who have fallen into a difficult social situation, to start the practice of working individually with unemployed and socially inactive women, to effectively organize activities to support employment and develop entrepreneurship among women, to adequately organize activities to protect women's reproductive health, to eliminate the organizational subordination of the Republican "Family" scientific-practical Centre and to address the lack of necessary sources of financing, to study family problems and to develop practical, scientifically based proposals for their elimination, it is important to organize the effective performance of the tasks assigned to them.*

Keywords: *women, girls, support, family and private business, profession, craft.*

INTRODUCTION

During the transition of Uzbekistan to a new stage of development, raising the system of all-round support for all women to a higher level and further increasing the place and role of women in society are becoming increasingly important. However, today the following problems remain in supporting women and increasing their social activity;

studying the problems of women, especially women in rural areas;

finding unemployed women who are in high demand in labor market training in professions;

providing employment;

and involving them in family and private entrepreneurship. Additionally, crafts have not been systematically implemented;

In the period when New Uzbekistan was developing, it is important to develop technologies for improving pedagogical and psychological aspects. is an urgent issue.

In this regard, a number of studies are being carried out in our republic. For example, in Annex 1 of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-87 dated March 7, 2022, in the national program for increasing the activity of women in all aspects of the economic, political and social life of the country in 2022-2026 in Uzbekistan, "Ensuring gender equality and expanding the rights and opportunities of all women" is defined as one of the priority goals within the framework of "National goals and tasks in the field of sustainable development until 2030".

To achieve this goal, it is necessary to expand programs that support women in realizing their rights and interests in the socioeconomic sphere.

In 2022 - 2026, the National Program for Increasing the Activity of Women in All Aspects of the Country's Economic, Political and Social Life (hereinafter referred to as the National Program) outlined the main directions of the state policy for supporting women.

The national programmer includes the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "On State Policy Regarding Youth", "On Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence", and "Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" on "the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the decision of the Senate of the Supreme Assembly of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the strategy for achieving gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", which generally recognized principles and norms of international law, prepared in accordance with the provisions of the international agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other legal documents.

The national programmer considers women's rights an integral part of human rights, and it is a set of measures for comprehensive support of women based on the principle of "for human dignity".

The development and implementation of the national programme serve as important factors in creating the necessary conditions for the full participation of women in the political, economic, social and cultural life of society on the basis of equal rights.

Funds necessary for their life needs are allocated from special funds aimed at providing financial support for women.

In particular, in 2018-2021, more than 5,600 women in difficult social situations were paid for the initial installment of the housing payment; nearly 20,000 women with disabilities received wheelchairs, hearing aids and other rehabilitation tools; approximately 18 thousand women were given preferential loans for establishing family and private businesses, and 500 women were paid for the costs of surgery.

By working with the "Women's Register", a system of support for women in need of social assistance will be created, and in 2021 alone, approximately 900 thousand women will be provided with socioeconomic, medical, legal and psychological support. Approximately one trillion soums were allocated.

The system of paying contract fees for studies of needy girls who have lost their parents or one of them, single women without a breadwinner has been introduced, and the number of grant places for girls from needy families for admission to higher education institutions doubled.

To finance business projects aimed at creating jobs for women, the practice of allocating loans with a 6-month grace period was launched, within the framework of the "Every family is an entrepreneur" program, approximately 126,000 women were given preferential loans.

More than 6 trillion soums of loans were allocated to nearly 215,000 families for the development of family entrepreneurship. A total of 55,000 women were trained by entrepreneurship and vocational centers, and were involved in crafting and homemaking.

As part of five important initiatives, sewing shops were established in remote areas, and 10,000 women were employed. Approximately 22 billion soums of initial contributions were paid to 1,250 women for the purchase of housing. Every year, 28 talented women were awarded the Zulfiya State Prize, and the laureates of the prize were admitted to the bachelor's and master's levels of higher education without entrance exams on the basis of a state grant. A "reputable woman" badge was established, and 855 activists were awarded this badge during the past period.

On the basis of the state order, a system of providing employment to the population and creating new jobs, as well as a procedure for recording the seniority of self-employed citizens, was established, and the share of women employed in the informal sector was reduced by 27%. Strong legal frameworks have been created to protect women from oppression and violence. In particular, a procedure for issuing a protection warrant providing state protection to a victim of oppression and violence was established, and through this procedure, more than 35,000 women who suffered from violence were protected from 2020-2021.

Approximately 100,000 women's appeals were resolved in 2021 alone through the 1211 short-number "hotline" that operates around the clock for women's appeals.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

At the beginning of our research, we studied the facilities and opportunities for women's education and professional development under the current conditions, as well as the relevant requirements.

The Republican Centre for the Rehabilitation and Adaptation of Women and its 14 regional and 14 exemplary inters district centers were established, and psychological, legal, medical and other types of assistance were provided to approximately 50 thousand women in these centres. In 2020-2021, neighbourhood activists reconciled approximately 50,000 families who were on the verge of divorce, legalized marriages in more than 20,000 families, and ended the turmoil of approximately 6,000 families. Centres for preparing youth for family life were established in all districts and cities.

During 2021, more than 90,000 married persons were trained by these centres free of charge on issues related to family-legal relations, the psychology of family life, the family economy and budget, the basics of reproductive health, and the strengthening of spiritual and moral values. Moreover, during the transition of Uzbekistan to a new stage of development, raising the system of all-round support to all women to a higher level and further increasing the place and role of women in society are becoming increasingly important.

However, today, the following problems remain in supporting women and further increasing their social activity:

- studying the problems of women, especially women in rural areas, training unemployed women in professions that are in high demand in the labor market, providing them with work, involving them in family and private entrepreneurship, handicraft cultivation is not carried out in a systematic way;

- To provide social, psychological and material support to women in need of help and who have fallen into a serious social situation, including women with disabilities and elderly women in need of care, to remove them from the state of need-focused work is not organized effectively;

- The problems of 15,000 women who need to improve their living conditions have not been fully resolved;

- the scope of activities aimed at increasing the legal culture of women, eliminating the factors and conditions that caused violations committed by them, and promoting legal consequences is insufficient;

- promotional work and methodological and practical work on the procedures for providing preferential loans (including) to women in need of social protection and low-income families for effective use of homestead land, allocation of subsidies to them and provision of employment there are weaknesses in the support system;

- Provide medical and social services to women in need of medical assistance in the region, especially in remote villages, identify sick women in serious condition, in a timely manner; and treat women with obvious signs of disability the periodicity of examination for girls is not regular;

- studying and helping to solve the problems of children growing up in families that have lost their breadwinners and on the verge of divorce, in single-parent families, and in families of women who have left their place of residence for a long time, social and psychological support work is not organized;

- Measures to train women released from penal institutions for professions, ensure their employment, and solve other problems in a timely manner are not up to the required level;

- In regions, especially in villages, a system of identifying the talents of adolescent girls in real time and helping them to realize them has not been introduced;

- Propagation on family, life culture, medical culture, respect for national values, and increasing the role of mothers-in-law in strengthening families among adolescent girls and young brides in the neighborhoods has not been effectively launched;

The "Women's Advisory Councils" in the neighborhoods provide effective public control over the study of women's problems and their timely solution, methodical and practical support and encouragement to increase their social activity. not done.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis of related provide research shows that our objective is to increase the social psychological training of women in our republic to improve the training of women in the process of increasing their social activity in choosing a profession.

Support for women in need of social protection support for women with disabilities or raising children with disabilities;

To support needy women who need to repair their homes and live in slums;

Support for needy women without breadwinners;

Comprehensive support for elderly women in need of care;

Helping to ensure the employment of needy women included in the "Women's register" and to start their own business.

The Decree of the President of March 7, 2022 "On measures to further accelerate work on systematic support of families and women" was adopted. The document was published in UzA. On the basis of improving the pedagogical aspects of increasing the social activity of women and girls, students should be independent, have an active citizenship position, take initiative, use media resources and information and communication technologies wisely in their activities, consciously choose a profession, engage in healthy competition and develop general cultural skills.

Basic competences: Communicative competence;

Information processing competence;

The competence of self-development as a person;

Socially active civic competence;

Universal competences;

Mathematical literacy is divided into competence to be aware of and use science and technology news. It is necessary for a person to engage in personal, social, economic and professional relationships in his life take his or her place in society solve the problems he or she faces,; and, most importantly, be competitive in his or her field and profession. In addition, in the

process of mastering each academic subject in education, specific competences related to the field are also formed for students based on the uniqueness and content of this subject.

The process of developing the art of embroidery and education in the field of folk crafts to increase the social activity of women and girls is closely related to the socioeconomic and political development of our country. During the rule of the former Soviets, the embroidery industry was completely destroyed. As a result of this process, social and political changes in society deprived this type of applied art of economic and material resources for decades. "For a long time, almost no one was interested in the art of embroidery, because this type of art was not worthy of attention, it was considered an art of feudalism."

Art historians who are engaged in the art of folk crafts emphasize that until the 50 s of the 20th century, the art of embroidery was not developed in the former Soviet state, but other directions of folk crafts were developed. [1]

By the 1950 s, embroidery factories were opened in large cities. During this period, interest in traditional embroidery crafts began to increase. Since that time, S.S. Bulatov, R. Khasanov, Associate Professor R. Shobaratov, Q. Kasimov, A. Turdialiev, O. Khudayorova and others have conducted research on solving the problems of training specialists in the field of embroidery of folk arts and crafts [2].

In particular, Professor Bulatov S.S., in his "Uzbek Folk Applied Decorative Art" methodical manual, described conditions for organizing and conducting classes on folk decorative art, theoretical and methodological bases of teaching and the programs, and an explanatory dictionary of terms was given. [3] Additionally, in the "Hanchkorlik" manual, the oldest group of Uzbek folk decorative art is dedicated to harching carving. It describes the history of the development of the art of ganchkor and the methods of teaching the profession to young people. Shobaratov's "composition" training manual shows the organization of the educational process of teaching applied art, and the goals and tasks of the composition of classes. The study guide, combined with other specialized subjects, helps to supplement the acquired knowledge of the students with the next knowledge. [4]

Professor R. Khasanov's textbook "Methodology of Fine Art Teaching at School" contains all the theoretical and methodical knowledge necessary for teaching methods of fine and applied art[5]. R. Khasanov's instructional manual titled "Methodology of pattern drawing in elementary grades" provides enough information about the specific features of pattern drawing, colors and their use, characteristics of colors, and pattern compositions [6]

Q.Kasimov's monographic work titled "Painting" describes the development of the art of painting, the theoretical foundations of training for the content of the painting circle, and the methodology of teaching pattern making [7].

According to the researchers, it is necessary to systematically work with personnel (from general education and vocational training in vocational schools to activities dedicated to improving the skills of direct performers masters in craft enterprises) and to this system vocational, technical and artistic secondary schools. Conducting work covering the teaching process in educational institutions provides effective results.

Madamin Berdiev's book "People's Handicrafts", published in 2005, played an important role in training embroiderers in graphic design. The book was created on the basis of the experience of training and teaching in various fields of crafts, including embroidery, at the School of Crafts and Arts of Uzbekistan.

During this period, a small number of specialists were trained in our country only at the Tashkent Art Vocational and Technical Educational Institution (now the Benkov Republican Art College), and students at this educational institution acquired specialties such as craftsmen and engravers of stamps.

This educational institution has experience teaching general and special subjects in the field of basic embroidery vocational training. In educational workshops, special attention is given to mastering various methods of artistic processing of fabric.

Although the curriculum has the same subjects, each educational institution works on the basis of its own specially designed programs in teaching skills, composition, material science and embroidery technology. This is the most important feature of educational institutions. Every traditional center for the production of embroidered products has limitations in terms of the compositional structure of the products, the materials, and technologies used and the technical methods used for product preparation. It is this craftsman who forms the basis of training masters and working on compositions. The compositions in each regional center reflected a single image an image related to the development and progress of traditions and innovations, modern trends, and the art of embroidery.

In particular, in today's vocational colleges, the study of theory and practice is carried out primarily through the study of fine arts. In addition to practical sciences, special attention is given to the teaching of theoretical sciences: the history of folk-art crafts, the history of arts, the history of methods, and similar subjects that form the necessary artistic worldview in young professionals.

In the system of tasks related to compositions, tasks related to the design of elegant volume products are also included. Improving the implementation of projects is reflected in the quality of creating a product from the material, and this process is carried out on the basis of approved training plans. For example, the basics of composition are studied in the 1st year. The assignments of this course include natural drawings of plants and their transformation (transformation), - decorative processing, and voluminous embroidery. In the 2nd year, they made embroidery stitches (loop, pop, chain, printed and Iraqi). In the 3rd year, they learn the methods of animal shape, taking into account the preparation of fabric.

The distinctive features of composition education in the artistic processing of fabrics in specialized schools and vocational colleges are as follows:

- First, teaching the ancient traditional craft of embroidery in Uzbekistan to future teachers of technology education on the basis of IT will lead to understanding of this craft as a component of the system of historical exchange of generations. Therefore, in the context of consistent and continuous development, teachers can guide students not only to learn about the technologies used to create embroidery products, but also to try to understand artistic ideas. In the course of education, future teachers learn traditional methods of embroidery in the preparation of handicrafts;

-Second, the influence of modern production traditions on the development of embroidery is manifested in the process of fabric processing as an embroidery technique. Future teachers will not only create decorations using the embroidery method but also create small works of art, as well as small pictorial compositions and embroidered products that are part of crafts;

- Third, students acquire knowledge, skills, and abilities related to the creation of folk handicraft products and are directed to create embroidery samples. As one of the main issues of composition education, future teachers of technology education envisage the combination of a composition system with the construction of small-scale embroidery products;

-Fourth, the introduction of new artistic trends (avant-garde currents) affects the emergence of compositions used in the processing of materials other than embroidery forms.

Thus, we can distinguish the main components of artistic and creative development typical of students in the artistic processing of fabrics in vocational colleges that prepare master craftsmen. The development of artistic perception is carried out through communication with craftsmen, and through studying museum collections.

During the communication process, the emotional experiences that help girls master traditional ways of working with needle, sozona (cloth), and angishvona (wearing to protect fingers from needle) are collected. For the development of the artistic memories and fantasies of the students of future technology education, artistic and creative compositional assignments are given, aimed at understanding what was seen in museums and in practice.

The extent of the worldview of teachers is reflected in educational projects where their associative thinking abilities are determined. The analysis of step-by-step assignments and diploma theses showed that future teachers should actively work with artistically realized, methodized forms of education. At the end of the educational process, future students will master compositional methods aimed at creating expressive artistic images.

Learners are trained in comprehensive methods of working with this material in the process of decorating fabric. In the 1st year, in the process of creating sets of simple, flat, elegant compositions, students learn the basic methods of gluing embroidery products. Special attention is given to the techniques of engraving, hammering, chipping, and casting. This process is explained by the invitation to work of teachers and masters to work, who bring traditional methods of artistic processing to fabrics. The various composite tasks used in the educational process are becoming more complex, which in turn leads to the deepening of students' knowledge, skills and abilities.

CONCLUSION

The analysis of the conducted research showed that the education of women, general professional training in choosing a profession, preparation for professional activity on the basis of pedagogical and psychological basis, and the comprehensive support system for all women is highly important during the transition of Uzbekistan to a new stage of development. However, today, the following problems remain in supporting women and increasing their social activity,; studying the problems of women, especially women in rural areas, and finding unemployed women who are in high demand in the labor market. It is necessary to establish technological approaches to systematize the work of training in professions, providing employment, and widely involving them in family and private entrepreneurship, and handicrafts.

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